

Which gene combination to test in wet lab? A demonstration of machine learning based search engine using ETC-1922159 static data

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Abstract

Biologists/oncologists often search for a range of combinations of genes/proteins that work synergistically in cells in various processes. This search is often difficult. To address this issue, a design of a machine learning based search engine was published recently. To demonstrate the effectiveness of this search engine on real life data sets, the data set containing recordings of up/down regulated genes generated from colorectal cancer cells which were treated with Porcupine-WNT inhibitor drug ETC-1922159 was taken. The regulation of the genes were recorded individually, but it is still not known which higher (≥ 2) order gene combinations might be playing a greater role after the administration of the drug. The adapted engine revealed the priority of these higher order unknown/untested/unexplored as well as wet lab tested combinations, among the up/down-regulated genes in static data. Based on these rankings, biologists/oncologists would not have to struggle to discover a particular gene/protein combination of interest for further wet lab test, that might be involved in a particular phenomena.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer / Gene combination / Machine learning / Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159 / Sensitivity analysis

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[☆]Which gene combination to test in wet lab?

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1. Introduction

1.1. Impact statement

Which gene combination to test in wet lab? This is a fundamental problem that biologists/oncologists face in their search for potential breakthroughs that could help understand the mechanism of cell biology leading to scientific discoveries and therapeutic interventions. In biology/oncology, one is faced with the problem of exploring relevant unknown biological hypotheses in the form of myriad of combinations of factors that might be affecting a pathway under certain conditions. Currently, a major persisting

problem is to cherry pick the combinations based on expert advice, literature survey or guesses for investigation. This entails investment in time, energy and expenses at various levels of research. To address these issues, a search engine design was recently published, which showed promise by revealing existing confirmatory published wet lab results. Additionally and of import, an adaptation of the published engine mined up a range of unexplored/untested/unknown combinations of genetic factors in the cell signaling pathways that were affected by ETC-1922159 enantiomer, a PORCN-WNT inhibitor, after the colorectal cancer cells were treated with the drug. This work demonstrates how a machine learning based search engine prioritizes combinations of genes, by revealing conserved rankings across different sensitivity methods/mathematical formulations in a data set from real life pathological scenario. These point to efficacy and the potential of the search engine, which might prove to be a valuable tool for oncologists/(developmental,molecular)biologists.

1.2. Summary

Hitherto, biologists/oncologists struggle with problem of finding/locating gene/protein combinations that might be necessary in understanding the mechanism of a pathway in (normal/pathological) cell biology. Using advanced machine learning based search engine, I show that it is possible to reveal these combinations (whether tested/untested, explored/unexplored) that might be working synergistically in a cell. The search engine has already been published recently. Here, I demonstrate that an adaptation of the search engine tested on real life pathological (colorectal cancer) data set, treated with a drug, reveals conserved rankings of combinations across different mathematical formulations of sensitivity methods that capture the strength of influence of factors (here genes/proteins) that affect a signaling pathway, using powerful support vector ranking algorithm. More importantly, the work reveals ground-breaking results in the form of higher order (un)explored/(un)tested combinations of genes/proteins (as biological hypotheses). Because of the above point, biologists/oncologists will be able to narrow down their search to particular combinations that are ranked and, if a synergistic functioning is confirmed in wet lab, will be able to study the mechanism between the components of a combination, in the cell. The search engine design is not only limited to one dataset and a range of combinations of genes/proteins. The framework can be applied/modified to all problems where one is interested in searching for particular combinations of factors involved in a particular phenomena.

1.3. Chronological literature review regarding ranking of genes

In the analysis of microarray data the identification of differential expression is paramount. In one of the earliest works, Broberg (2003) outline a method for finding an optimal test statistic to rank genes with respect to differential expression. His test of the method show that it allows generation of top gene lists that give few false positives and few false negatives. Estimation of the false-negative as well as the false-positive rate lies at the heart of the method.

Feature ranking prioritize features via their individual importance and is used as a feature selection techniques. Traditional feature ranking criteria produce inconsis-

tent ranking results even with light perturbations in training samples when applied to high dimensional and small-sized gene expression data. To address this inconsistency, multi-criterion combination strategy is used, but one problem encountered in combining multiple criteria is the score normalization. Yang and Mao (2010) analyse problems in existing methods and then propose a new gene importance transformation algorithm. Their experimental studies on three popular gene expression datasets show that the multi-criterion combination based on the proposed score correction and normalization produces gene rankings with improved robustness.

Standard rank aggregation methods to provide prioritized gene lists, are ill-suited for biological settings where the gene lists are inherently noisy. Kolde et al. (2012) propose a robust rank aggregation (RRA) method that detects genes that are ranked consistently better than expected under null hypothesis of uncorrelated inputs and assigns a significance score for each gene. Their underlying probabilistic model makes the algorithm parameter free and robust to outliers, noise and errors. Significance scores also provide a rigorous way to keep only the statistically relevant genes in the final list.

Xiao et al. (2014) define a gene significance score π -value by combining expression fold change which measure biological relevance and statistical significance (P-value), and explored its statistical properties. On comparing existing methods, π -value based approach was found to be more robust in selecting differentially expressed genes, with the largest area under curve in its receiver operating characteristic curve. Their application of π -value to GSEA showed results comparable to P-value and t-statistic based methods, with added protection against false discovery in certain situations. Finally, in a gene functional study of breast cancer profiles, they showed using π -value helps elucidating otherwise overlooked important biological functions.

As challenges to food security increase, the demand for lead genes for improving crop production is growing. However, genetic screens of plant mutants typically yield very low frequencies of desired phenotypes. Ransbotyn et al. (2015) present a computational approach for selecting candidate genes for screening insertion mutants by combining ranking of *Arabidopsis thaliana* regulatory genes according to their expression in response to multiple abiotic stresses (Multiple Stress [MST] score) and stress-responsive RNA co-expression network analysis to select candidate multiple stress regulatory (MSTR) genes. This screening approach based on combining gene ranking and network analysis can be applicable to enhancing identification of genes regulating additional processes in plants and other organisms provided that suitable transcriptome data are available.

RNA-sequencing is rapidly becoming the method of choice for studying the full complexity of transcriptomes, however with increasing dimensionality, accurate gene ranking is becoming increasingly challenging. Jia et al. (2015) proposed a gene ranking method that implements discriminant non-negative matrix factorization (DNMF) for RNA-seq data by incorporating Fisher's discriminant criteria and setting the reduced dimension as two. DNMF learned two factors to approximate the original gene expression data, abstracting the up-regulated or down-regulated metagene by using the sample label information. In the gene ranking stage, all the genes are ranked as a descending sequence according to the differential values of the metagene weights. They show via Gene Set Enrichment Analysis that DNMF outweighed other methods and it is computationally efficient for the analysis of differential gene expression and gene

ranking for RNA-seq data.

In functional genomics experiments, researchers select genes to follow-up or validate from a long list of differentially expressed genes. Often, sharp thresholds are used to bin genes into groups such as significant/non-significant or fold change above/below a cut-off value, and ad hoc criteria are also used such as favouring well-known genes. p-values, fold-changes, and other outcomes are treated as equally important, and relevant genes may be overlooked with such an approach. Lazic (2015) propose desirability functions as a way to integrate multiple selection criteria for ranking, selecting, and prioritising genes. These functions map any variable to a continuous 0–1 scale, where one is maximally desirable and zero is unacceptable. Multiple selection criteria are then combined to provide an overall desirability that is used to rank genes.

Microarray expression data have been collected for studying the underlying biological mechanisms of disease and an application for understanding the mechanism is by constructing a gene regulatory network (GRN) which requires gene selection as a key criteria. Choosing a set of genes for the structure of the network is highly desirable and Mishra and Mishra (2016) propose two methods. The first approach is called Information gain, where the dataset is reformed and fused with another distinct algorithm called Trace Ratio (TR) while the second method is the implementation of their projected modified TR algorithm, where the scoring base for finding weight matrices was re-designed. Both the methods' efficiency was shown with different classifiers that include variants of the Artificial Neural Network classifier and the Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier. Their study confirmed that both of the proposed methods worked well and offered high accuracy with a lesser number of iterations as compared to the original Trace Ratio algorithm.

Noise generated during the assay and analytical processes has the ability to disrupt accurate interpretation of genomic studies. deAndres Galiana et al. (2016) applied a sequence of ranking methods to damp noise associated with microarray outputs, and then tested the utility of the approach in three disease indications using publically available datasets. Their study theoretically analyzed the effect of noise in phenotype prediction problems showing that it can be expressed as a modeling error that partially falsifies the pathways. Next, they performed sensitivity analysis for the main gene ranking methods to different types of noise. Finally, they studied the predictive accuracy of the gene lists provided by these ranking methods in synthetic data and in three different datasets to better understand the translational aspects of their findings.

Till now, all above methods describe ways to rank genes. However they do not address the issue of ranking gene combinations which are known to work synergistically in cells. In 2016, the unpublished methodology and results of Sinha (2024) were presented as poster in the EMBO Wnt, 2016, Brno, Czech Republic (for static data) and the Berkeley Cell Symposia: Technology, Biology and Data Science, 2016, Berkeley, USA (for time series data). To the author's knowledge, this is the first work of its kind that addresses the issue of revealing unknown gene combinations that might be working and affecting a cell signaling pathway, based on machine learning based search engine. In a follow through of the adaptation of this work (now in Sinha (2024)) in 2016, in (August 6 - 11) 2017, Sinha (2018) presented the rankings results for ETC-1922159 data in Wnt Signaling: A Pathway Implicated in Animal Development, Stem Cell Control and Cancer (Wnt Gordon Research Conference) , Stoweflake Conference

Center, Vermont, USA. Across all search engines, the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. Sinha (2018) use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

Choosing a ranking metric in Gene Set Enrichment Analysis has critical impact on results of pathway enrichment analysis. Zyla et al. (2017) show that the Moderated Welch Test has the best overall sensitivity and Minimum Significant Difference has the best overall specificity of gene set analysis. When the number of non-normally distributed genes is high, using Baumgartner-Weiss-Schindler test statistic gave better outcomes. Also, it finds more enriched pathways than other tested metrics, which might induce new biological discoveries.

Nim et al. (2017) present a computational strategy to systematically rank and investigate a large number (2^{10} – 2^{20}) of clinically testable gene sets, using combinatorial gene subset generation and disease-free survival (DFS) analyses. They integrated protein–protein interaction networks, gene expression, DNA methylation, and copy number data, in association with DFS profiles from patient clinical records. Combinatorial enumeration of all possible subsets of n genes with DFS helps isolate k gene sets based on statistical significance.

The computational cost of finding a q -tuple of genes that scores highest under a given metric is $O(G^q)$, where G is the total number of genes. This cost is often problematic or prohibitive in practice (even for $q = 2$), as the number of genes G is often in the order of tens of thousands. Khamesipour and Kagaris (2019) show that this computational cost can be significantly reduced by excluding from consideration genes whose behavior is almost identical in the two classes and therefore their inclusion in any q -tuple is rather non-informative. By filtering out genes whose Area Under the Curve (AUC) value is below a user-chosen threshold, as determined by a procedure that they describe dramatic reductions in the run times are obtained while maintaining the same classification accuracy.

Aevermann et al. (2021) described a machine learning-based marker gene selection algorithm, NS-Forest version 2.0, which leverages the nonlinear attributes of random forest feature selection and a binary expression scoring approach to discover the mini-

mal marker gene expression combinations that optimally capture the cell type identity represented in complete single-cell RNA sequencing transcriptional profiles.

A more recent work on finding gene combinations was developed in 2023, by Xia et al. (2023). Xia et al. (2023) conduct High Multiplicity of Perturbations and Cellular Indexing of Transcriptomes and Epitopes (HMPCITE-seq) to find combinations of genes whose joint targeting improves antigen-presenting cell activity and enhances their ability to activate T cells.

Using single-cell gene expression datasets, Granados et al. (2024) identified pathway expression motifs, defined as recurrent expression profiles that are broadly distributed across diverse cell types and involved combinatorial co-expression of multiple components.

1.4. PORCN-WNT inhibitors

The regulation of the Wnt pathway is dependent on the production and secretion of the WNT proteins. Thus, the inhibition of a causal factor like PORCN which contributes to the WNT secretion has been proposed to be a way to interfere with the Wnt cascade, which might result in the growth of tumor. Several groups have been engaged in such studies and known PORCN-WNT inhibitors that have been made available till now are IWP-L6 Chen et al. (2009) & Wang et al. (2013), C59 Proffitt et al. (2013), LGK974 Liu et al. (2013) and ETC-1922159 Duraiswamy et al. (2015). In this study, the focus of the attention is on the implications of the ETC-1922159, after the drug has been administered. The drug is an enantiomer with a nanomolar activity and excellent bioavailability as claimed in Duraiswamy et al. (2015).

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

A recent design of a machine learning based search engine was published Sinha (2024), that ranks combinations of genes that might be working synergistically in cells in various processes. To demonstrate its efficacy in real life scenario, the data set containing recordings of up/down regulated genes generated from colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with PROCN-WNT inhibitor drug ETC-1922159 was taken Madan et al. (2016). The regulation of the genes were recorded individually, but in many cases, it is still not known which higher (≥ 2) order gene combinations might be playing a greater role in CRC. Here, I demonstrate that the rankings assigned to gene combinations at 2^{nd} order, by the search engine are conserved across the different sensitivity methods (and kernels/variants). This conservation points to the possible existence of the synergy between genes at the biological level. These ranked unknown biological hypotheses facilitate in narrowing down the investigation of ETC-1922159 affected synergistic-factors. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab for which the machine learning based search engine points appropriate rankings, however, it also reveals several other combinations which have not been tested/explored. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha (2018).

1.6. Why use this machine learning based search engine?

In my limited opinion, the following goals can be achieved using the published work -

1. Biologist/oncologist can download the available code in R (and with support from any personnel having R programming experience), and apply to their data sets to rank/prioritise unknown combinations of genes/proteins which might be working synergistically in a pathway.
2. Because of 1. biologist/oncologist will not have to struggle to search for combinations of interest. The rankings of the combinations shed light on how the combinations can be searched/located. Probably, this work will make life easier.
3. Based on these rankings, the modifications of the work will help in writing grant proposals for testing machine learning based discoveries. This will also help biologist/oncologist get financial support for their research.
4. Combinations of any order can be generated and ranked. However, computational resources might be required and the search engine might have to be fine tuned.
5. Finally, the work might help answer many questions in cell biology. Though experimental tests need to be conducted on the discoveries made by applying the above machine learning based pipeline.

2. Methods

2.1. Static data by Madan et al. (2016)

Data used in this research work was released in a publication by Madan et al. (2016). The ETC-1922159 was released in Singapore in July 2015 under the flagship of the Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR) and Duke-National University of Singapore Graduate Medical School (Duke-NUS). Note that the ETC-1922159 data show numerical point measurements that is as Madan et al. (2016) quote - "List of differentially expressed genes identified at three days after the start of ETC-159 treatment of colorectal tumors. Log2 fold-changes between untreated (vehicle, VEH) and ETC-159 treated (ETC) tumors are reported." The numerical point measurements of differentially expressed genes were recorded using the following formulation of fold changes in equation 1 (see Tusher et al. (2001), Choe et al. (2005) and Witten and Tibshirani (2007)).

$$\log_2 \frac{VEH_{avg}}{ETC_{avg}} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Revealing higher order biological hypotheses via sensitivity analysis and insilico ranking algorithm

In the trial experiments on ETC-1922159 Madan et al. (2016), a list of genes (2500±) have been reported to be up and down regulated after the drug treatment and a time buffer of 3 days. Some of the transcript levels of these genes have been recorded and

the experimental design is explained elaborately in the same manuscript. In the list are also available unknown or uncharacterised proteins that have been recorded after the drug was administered. These have been marked as "- -" in the list (Note - In this manuscript these uncharacterised proteins have been marked as "XXM", where $M = 1, 2, 3, \dots$). The aim of this work is to reveal unknown/unexplored/untested biological hypotheses that form higher order combinations. For example, it is known that the combinations of WNT-FZD or RSPO-LGR-RNF play significant roles in the Wnt pathway. But the $n \geq 2, 3, \dots$ -order combinations out of $N(> n)$ genes forms a vast combinatorial search forest that is extremely tough to investigate due to the humongous amount of combinations. Currently, a major problem in biology is to cherry pick the combinations based on expert advice, literature survey or random choices to investigate a particular combinatorial hypothesis. The current work aims to reveal these unknown/unexplored/untested combinations by prioritising these combinations using a potent support vector ranking algorithm Joachims (2006). This cuts down the cost in time/energy/investment for any investigation concerning a biological hypothesis in a vast search space.

The pipeline works by computing sensitivity indices for each of these combinations and then vectorising these indices to connote and form discriminative feature vector for each combination. The ranking algorithm is then applied to a set of combinations/sensitivity index vectors and a ranking score is generated. Sorting these scores leads to prioritization of the combinations. Note that these combinations are now ranked and give the biologists a chance to narrow down their focus on crucial biological hypotheses in the form of combinations which the biologists might want to test. Analogous to the webpage search engine, where the click of a button for a few key-words leads to a ranked list of web links, the pipeline uses sensitivity indices as an indicator of the strength of the influence of factors or their combinations, as a criteria to rank the combinations.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractETCdata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 50 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 50 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence after the ETC-1922159 has been administered. Note that 1 means lowest rank and 2743 is the highest rank for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Design for static data from Madan et al. (2016)

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n-1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Note that the ETC-1922159 data show numerical point measurements that is as Madan et al. (2016) quote "List of differentially expressed genes identified at three days after the start of ETC-159 treatment of colorectal tumors. Log2 fold-changes between untreated (vehicle, VEH) and ETC-159 treated (ETC) tumors are reported." Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 50 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format (See .R code in mainscrip-2-2.R in google drive). Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha (2017), which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims (2006) is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tunned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims (2006). This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractETCdata.R") • use source("mainScript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R"). Link to download the code has been provided at the end of this manuscript.

2.5. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha (2024) and its unpublished adaptation for ETC-1922159 data in Sinha (2018).

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

2.6. Regarding data

Note that the recordings of the regulations of genes (available in the supplementary table of the source of data) after the ETC-1922159 treatment of cancer cells was done 3 days after the administration of medicine. Am not sure if the data can be reproduced exactly again, as the conditions and quality of cells on which the drug administration was done, will not remain same. The wet lab experimental procedure may be the same, but the recordings of genes might differ from case to case basis, even when the same drug is administered. However, the phenotype or effects of the medicine might be same, like suppression of growth of cancer cells.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Interpretation of 2nd order ranking with RAD51AP1 using HSIC-rbf density based sensitivity index

For example, the ranking generated for second order combination for RAD51AP1 is enlisted below. What these rankings suggests is that after the treatment of ETC-1922159, genes along with their combination with RAD51AP1 were prioritised and this gives the biologists a clue to study the behaviour of RAD51AP1 along with other genes in colorectal cancer case.

1 HOXB9-RAD51AP1

2 NASP-RAD51AP1

3 MCM3-RAD51AP1

•

•

2741 RAD51AP1-CDX2

2742 RAD51AP1-LPCAT3

2743 RAD51AP1-EIF2B1

DNA repair is an important aspect in maintaining the proper and healthy functioning for the cells in the human body. Failure in DNA repair process can lead to aberrations as well as tumorous stages. There are various types of damages that a DNA can go through, one of which is the DNA double strand breaks (DSB) that can be repaired via homologous recombination (HR). RAD51 plays a central role in HR and is known to function in the three phases of HR namely : presynapsis, synapsis and post-synapsis Krejci et al. (2012). Recently, RAD51 has been implicated as a negative/poor prognostic marker for colorectal adenocarcinoma and has been found to be highly expressed Tennstedt et al. (2013). A negative/poor prognostic marker indicates that it is harder to control the malignancy. Since RAD51 helps in the repair of the DNA damage via HR and is implicated as a poor prognostic marker in colorectal adenocarcinoma, this suggests its functionality in maintaining genomic stability and therapeutic resistance to cancer drugs. Mechanistically, RAD51AP1 facilitates RAD51 during the repairing process by binding with RAD51 via two DNA binding sites, thus helping in the D-loop formation in the HR process Dunlop et al. (2012) & Modesti et al. (2007).

In context of the ETC-1922159 treatment, a series of 2nd order rankings have been generated for RAD51AP1. Using the above pipeline can help decipher biological implications. BRCA2 is known to be a main mediator in the HR process along with RAD51 and interact with RAD51 in various ways Davies and Pellegrini (2007), Esashi et al. (2007), Ayoub et al. (2009) & Schlacher et al. (2011). A relative low rank of 458 between RAD51AP1-BRCA2 states that after the ETC-1922159 treatment the combination gets low priority indicating that as there is suppression of CRC, the genomic stability of the cancer cells is affected by rendering the DNA repairing capacity of RAD51AP1-BRCA2 ineffective to a certain extent. PPA2 is a tumor suppressor that regulates many signaling pathways and plays crucial role in cell transformation Seshacharyulu et al. (2013). PPA2 is known to be highly suppressed in colorectal cancer case Cristóbal et al. (2014). The relatively high ranking of 2675 for RAD51AP1-PPA2 combination indicates two points (a) the ineffectiveness of RAD51AP1 to provide genomic stability to cancer cell and (b) the over expression of PPA2 after ETC-1922159 was administered. Also, SET is a known PPA2 inhibitor and is observed to be highly overexpressed in colorectal cancer cases. In relation to the ranking of RAD51AP1-PPA2, after the administration of the drug, RAD51AP1-SET showed a lower rank of 2227.

The x-ray repair cross complementing XRCC family is known to work as a mediator or stabilizer for RAD51 during the HR process Krejci et al. (2012). The relatively low rank of 366 for the RAD51AP1-XRCC2 indicates that the effectiveness for DNA repair capability is affected by ETC-1922159 drug as the tumor growth is suppressed. This is further confirmed by the fact that XRCC2 forms complex with paralogues of RAD51, i.e RAD51C–RAD51D–XRCC2 for DNA repair Masson et al. (2001) & Yokoyama et al. (2004). Other members of XRCC like XRCC1, XRCC6BP1 and XRCC6, showed relatively higher rankings of 1874, 2398 and 2558. Not much is known about these 3 factors in colorectal cancer case. XRCC1 may be weakly implicated in the colorectal cancer cases as have been found in the case studies in Taiwan Yeh et al. (2005). Very little is known about XRCC6BP1 and in a risk score based analysis it was found that XRCC6BP1 acts as a tumor repressor with very low expression profile in colorectal cancer Diao et al. (2017). High rankings suggests that after ETC-1922159 treatment, the expression level of XRCC6BP1 is extremely high, indicating the establishment of genomic stability of health via suppression of cancer cells. Finally, the very high priority of XRCC6 only indicates its role as a tumor repressor and further wet lab analysis needs to be conducted to verify the effectiveness of the pipeline.

RNF43/ZNRF3 are known to negatively regulate the Wnt pathway by targeting the FZD family and leading to its degradation and thus acting as a hinderance to the Wnt pathway Feng and Gao (2015). In presence of members from RSPO and LGR family, the RNF43/ZNRF3 is degraded in the cell and this leads to enhancement of the Wnt signaling de Lau et al. (2014). In relation to the RAD51AP1, the ranking of RNF43 was found to be 1893 and the ranking of ZNRF3 was found to be 549, respectively, after the treatment of ETC-1922159. The lower ranking of ZNRF43 with RAD51AP1 might indicate some affinity between RAD51AP1-ZNRF43 in comparison to the high ranking of RAD51AP1-RNF43. This needs to be tested. LGR5 and LGR6 had associated low ranks for 327 and 161, respectively. After the administration of the drug, the LGR5, RNF43 and ZNRF43 were known to be downregulated Madan et al. (2016). These are evident from the low rankings in combination with RAD51AP1, except for RNF43. An implication of the above combination of rankings can be the fact that as the drug takes its affect, it has multiple consequences wherein the RNF43/ZNRF3 along with LGR5 is being degraded so that the signaling is inhibited and also the genomic instability of the cancer cells in instigated by the ineffectiveness of RAD51AP1 to help in DNA repair in cancer cells.

Such rankings hold promise for any biologists who is investigating a pathway for a particular phenomena and is faced with a vast combinatorial search forest. These rankings also provide confirmatory results for existing published wet lab affirmations.

3.2. HSF2-NK κ B-XRN2

NF-kappa-B-repressing factor or NKRF encodes a transcription factor that combines with some negative regulatory elements to repress NFKB responsive genes. After the treatment of ETC-159 in colorectal cancer cell lines, NKRF was found to be down regulated. Out of some 2744 down regulated genes, the search engine generated a ranking of 2nd order combinations of NKRF along with the remaining genes. 2nd

RANKING USING HSIC			
2RD ORDER RANKING W.R.T NKRF			
	Laplace	Linear	Rbf
NKRF-XRN2	1715	940	1382
NKRF-HSF2	1846	2616	473
2RD ORDER RANKING W.R.T HSF2			
	Laplace	Linear	Rbf
HSF2-XRN2	2284	2037	1661
NKRF-HSF2	251	27	115
2RD ORDER RANKING W.R.T XRN2			
	Laplace	Linear	Rbf
HSF2-XRN2	911	1048	946
NKRF-XRN2	1567	663	2424

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking using HSIC for different kernels. Total number of interactions per gene were 2743.

order ranking for HSF2 and XRN2 in light of the ranking of NKRF repressor of NFkB are also recorded. Table 1 contains prioritisation based on 3 different factors separately. This helps in 3 fold cross check across the combinations.

3.2.1. Ranking on confirmatory NKRF-XRN2 combination

In a recent publication (2017) in Memet et al. (2017) it has been shown that human G-patch protein NFkB repressing factor (NKRF) forms a pre-ribosomal sub-complex with the DEAH-box RNA helicase DHX15 and the 5'-3' exonuclease XRN2. NKRF is essential for recruitment of the exonuclease XRN2 to nucleolar pre-ribosomal complexes. The findings therefore reveal a novel pre-ribosomal subcomplex that plays distinct roles in the processing of pre-rRNAs and the turnover of excised spacer fragments. If one looks at the rankings of NKRF-XRN2 in in table 1, it shows a rank of 1715, 940 and 1382 using laplace, linear and rbf kernel respectively. These point to the level of down regulation that was recorded in wet lab. Though not too low, these ranks suggest of relatively correct convergence by the search engine on known biological hypothesis regarding NKRF and XRN2.

3.2.2. Ranking on confirmatory NKRF-HSF2 combination

In a recent publication (2017) by Coccia et al. (2017), it has been shown that NKRF is a nucleolar HSP essential for nucleolus homeostasis and cell survival under proteotoxic stress. HSF1, considered the master regulator of stress-induced transcriptional responses, controls the expression of cytoprotective heat shock proteins (HSPs), molecular chaperones/cochaperones constituting a major component of the cell protein quality control machinery essential to circumvent stress-induced degradation and aggregation of misfolded proteins. The paper shows that the combination of NKRF-HSF1 is essential for correct ribosomal RNA (rRNA) processing and preventing aberrant rRNA

precursors and discarded fragment accumulation. HOWEVER, work on NKRF-HSF2 has not been reported.

If one looks at the rankings of NKRF-HSF2 in table 1, it shows a rank of 1846, 2616 and 473 using laplace, linear and rbf kernel respectively. These point to the level of down regulation that was recorded in wet lab. Though not too consistent and encouraging for the laplace (1846) and linear (2616) kernel, the rbf kernel does point to a low order rank of 473 which might be worth considering. 473 points to the fact the NKRF-HSF2 was significantly down regulated after ETC-159 treatment in colorectal cancer. Wet lab tests for combination of unreported NKRF-HSF2 would be worth reporting and would confirm the efficacy of the engine.

3.2.3. Possible working scenarios

- Possible causal relation HSF2 \rightarrow NKRF \rightarrow XRN2 might exist
- HSF2-NKRF shows promise in HSF2 \rightarrow NKRF (251, 27, 115) instead of NKRF \rightarrow HSF2 (1846, 2616, 473)
- In rankings of HSF2, (HSF2 - XRN2) show low promise (2284, 2037, 1661); however, in rankings of XRN2, (HSF2 - XRN2) show better promise (911, 1048, 946)
- NKRF-XRN2 shows weak but favourable ranking (940 linear, 1382 rbf) in NKRF ranking and (1567 laplace, 663 linear)
- Wet lab tests on HSF2-NKRF-XRN2 will prove affects of HSF2 and will establish the effectiveness of the search engine.

3.3. MYC-HOXB8-EZH2

EZH2 encodes enhancer of zeste homolog 2 and is involved in transcriptional repression via epigenetic modifications. It has been found to be either mutated or over-expressed in many forms of cancer. Over expression of EZH2 leads to silencing of various tumor suppressor genes and thus implicating it for potential roles in tumorigenesis Simon and Lange (2008). EZH2 is a subunit of the highly conserved Polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) which executes the methylation of the histone H3 at lysine-27 O'Meara and Simon (2012). Thus targeting EZH2 has become a major research domain for cancer therapeutics Kim and Roberts (2016). In colon cancer, it has been shown that depletion of EZH2 has led to blocking of proliferation of the cancer Fussbroich et al. (2011). This indicates the fact that tumor suppressor genes get activated and lead to subsequent blocking of the cancer. Also, EZH2 is recruited by PAF to bind with β -catenin transcriptional complex for further Wnt target gene activation, independent of the EZH2 epigenetic modification activities Jung et al. (2013).

Consistent with these, ETC-15922159 treatment lead to down regulation of EZH2 in colorectal cancer samples Madan et al. (2016). This would have activated a lot of tumor suppressor genes that led to subsequent suppression of regrowth in treated cancer samples. More importantly, MYC directly upregulates core components of PRC2, EZH2 being one of them, in embryonic stem cells Neri et al. (2012). Neri et al. (2012) show that silencing of c-MYC and N-MYC Dardenne et al. (2016) lead to reduction in the expression of PRC2 and thus EZH2. Furthermore, in colorectal cancer cases, Satoh et al. (2017) show that knockdown of MYC led to decrease in EZH2 levels. Similar findings have been observed in Yamaguchi and Hung (2014), Chen et al. (2016) &

Fluge et al. (2009). Our in silico findings show consistent results with respect to this down regulation after assigning a low rank of 54 along with MYC-HOXB8.

More specifically, our in silico pipeline is able to approximate the value of the 3rd order combination of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 by assigning a rank that is consistent with wet lab findings of dual combinatorial behaviour of MYC-EZH2 and MYC-HOXB8. However, since the mechanism of combination of MYC-HOXB8 is not known hitherto, it would be interesting to confirm the behaviour of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 at 3rd order to reveal a portion of the Wnt pathway's modus operandi in colorectal cancer. Further wet lab tests on these in silico findings will confirm the efficacy of the search engine.

3.4. Identified/identified 2nd-order combinations

Table 2 shows the relative rankings apropos RNF43 for three different kernels. The genes that have been shown along with the RNF43 are known to be highly expressed in colorectal cancer cases and after the ETC-1922159 was administered. Here we show only a few of the rankings as a confirmatory result that supports the in silico findings of the pipeline. In the table, except for BMP7 and NKD1, while considering the majority rankings over the three different columns representing the kinds of kernels used with the HSIC density based method, we find that each one of them has been assigned a relatively low priority in the order of 2743 combinations. The implication of these low rankings indicate or confirm the effectiveness of the pipeline in assigning appropriate biologically induced priority to the ETC-1922159 influenced down regulation of these genes. Surprisingly, BMP7 Motoyama et al. (2008) and NKD1 Stancikova et al. (2015) are known to be highly expressed in colorectal cancer case and were down regulated after the drug treatment. But these were assigned high rank with RNF43. Mutations in RNF43 could be subdued after ETC-1922159 has suppressed the Wnt pathway as has been shown in Madan et al. (2016). NKD1 is enigmatic in nature and known to be a negative regulator of the Wnt pathway Larraguibel et al. (2015). Mutations in NKD1 have been found to be prevalent in colorectal cancer cases Guo et al. (2009). High rank might suggest that after the suppression of the cancer cells, the NKD1 is highly activated or the mutated version of NKD1, if present, are highly ineffective. Thus the RNF43-NKD1 acquires a high ranking by the engine and it is more likely that NKD1 is highly activated.

ZNRF3/RNF43 is known to be implicated in inhibiting the Wnt signaling via degradation of FZDs at the cell surface level de Lau et al. (2014) & Hao et al. (2016). Mutations in these can lead to aberrant signaling and mutated RNF43 were found to be suppressed after the ETC-1922159 treatment and the relatively low rank assigned to the combination points to effectiveness of the pipeline. Similarly, RRM2 which is involved in DNA repair Zhang et al. (2009), is implicated in the metastasis of colon cancer Liu et al. (2007) and was observed to be highly expressed in colorectal cancer cases Madan et al. (2016). With mutated RNF43, as the Wnt signaling is enhanced, there is possibility of increased tumorigenesis and RRM2 could synergistically work in tandem with RAD51AP1 (another contributor of genomic stability) to enhance the metastasis of CRC. Coincidentally, the pipeline gives a preferred low rank of 139 to RRM2-RAD51AP1 combination after the drug treatment, thus indicating that its inhibition

RANKING USING HSIC W.R.T RNF43			
2^{nd} odr comb.	rbf	laplace	linear
LGR5-RNF43	61	85	114
LGR6-RNF43	1652	805	939
RAD51AP1-RNF43	175	469	11
ZNRF3-RNF43	570	1603	404
RRM2-RNF43	556	667	442
MKI67-RNF43	1575	278	92
AXIN2-RNF43	531	51	482
ASCL2-RNF43	116	441	197
MCM4-RNF43	131	1142	204
RNF43-BMP7	2723	2701	2530
RNF43-NKD1	2635	2169	2226

Table 2: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking using HSIC for different kernels. Total number of interactions per gene were 2743.

in the suppressed cancer cells. The lower ranking of RRM2 along with the RNF43 points to the correct prioritization by the pipeline. Similar results were found for KI-67 (MKI67) which as an independent prognostic marker for CRC Melling et al. (2016) and MCM4, which play essential role in DNA replication Nishihara et al. (2008), are both highly expressed in colorectal cancer cases. AXIN2, like AXIN1, helps in the assembly of the destruction complex that facilitates in the degradation of β -catenin in the cytoplasm, thus negatively regulating the Wnt pathway Mazzoni and Fearon (2014). Mutations in AXIN family can lead to different subtypes of CRC. AXIN2 is also a transcriptional target for β -catenin and changes in protein levels of AXIN2 due to excessive β -catenin can negatively regulate the Wnt pathway in cancer cases. Mutations in RNF43 can lead to enhanced Wnt signaling which can then target the over expression of AXIN2 via β -catenin that might lead to negative feedback to the pathway at a later stage. After the ETC-1922159 treatment, AXIN2 was found to be down regulated. This implies that the drug is working at multiple levels to inhibit the Wnt pathway and the low ranking of the AXIN2-RNF43 combination assigned by the pipeline accounts for this fact.

ASCL2 has been found to play a major role in stemness in colon crypts and is implicated in colon cancer Zhu et al. (2012). Switching off the ASCL2 leads to a literal blockage of the stemness process and vice versa. At the downstream level, ASCL2 is regulated by TCF4/ β -catenin via non-coding RNA target named WiNTR-LINC1 Giakountis et al. (2016). Activation of ASCL2 leads to feedforward transcription of the non-coding RNA and thus a loop is formed which helps in the stemness and is highly effective in colon cancer. At the upstream level, ASCL2 is known act as a WNT/RSPONDIN switch that controls the stemness Schuijers et al. (2015). It has been shown that removal of RSPO1 led to decrease in the Wnt signaling due to removal of the FZD receptors that led to reduced expression of ASCL2. Also, low levels of LGR5 were observed due to this phenomena. The opposite happened by in-

creasing the RSPO1 levels. After the drug treatment, it was found that ASCL2 was highly suppressed pointing to the inhibition of stemness in the colorectal cancer cells. Also, Schuijers et al. (2015) show that by genetically disrupting PORCN or inducing a PORCN inhibitor (like IWP-2), there is loss of stem cell markers like LGR5 and RNF43, which lead to disappearance of stem cells and moribund state of mice. A similar affect can be found with ETC-1922159, where there is suppression of RNF43 and LGR5 that lead to inhibition of the Wnt pathway and thus the ASCL2 regulation. These wet lab evidences are confirmed in the relatively low ranking of the combination ASCL2-RNF43 via the inhibition of PORCN-WNT that leads to blocking of the stemness that is induced by ASCL2. Since ASCL2 is directly mediated by the WNT proteins, the recorded ASCL2-WNT10B combination showed low priority ranking of 488, 497 and 321 for rbf, laplace and linear kernels, respectively, thus indicating a possible connection between WNT10B and ASCL2 activation. WNT10B might be playing a crucial role in stemness. This is further confirmed by wet lab experiments in Reddy et al. (2016), which show BVES deletion results in amplified stem cell activity and Wnt signaling after radiation. WNT10B has been implicated in colorectal cancer Yoshikawa et al. (2007).

The foregoing descriptions confirm the effectiveness of the pipeline for a few cases and it is not possible to elucidate each and every combination in a single manuscript. The rankings have been made available for further tests and will help the investigator in narrowing down their focus on particular aspects of the signaling pathway in cancer cases.

3.5. Unidentified/(Un)identified 2^{nd} -order combinations

Hitherto, the 2^{nd} order combinations pertaining to known or recorded factors that have been affected by the ETC-1922159 have been prioritized and discussed. But there were some uncharacterized proteins that were also affected after the drug treatment and their behaviour might not be known in terms of higher order interactions. We now traverse the uncharted territory of unknown/unexplored/untested proteins whose transcript levels were recorded after the drug treatment. Note that we will be dealing with two different cases over here - (1) Unidentified/identified 2^{nd} order combinations and (2) Unidentified/unidentified 2^{nd} order combinations. In total 234 such unidentified proteins were recorded of which we show the interpretations of only a few. Note that the numbers like 1,13, 121 etc associated with XX DO NOT imply any sort of association and we do not assume anything about them. We just interpret the rankings of these unidentified factors with identified and unidentified factors. Table 3 represents these combinations, with the first 20 describing XX1-identified factor combinations and the next 16 describing XX1-unidentified factor combinations.

RANKING USING HSIC W.R.T XX1			
2^{nd} odr comb.	rbf	laplace	linear
UNIDENTIFIED-IDENTIFIED COMBINATIONS			
XX1-RAD51AP1	199	434	36
RRM2-XX1	131	185	138
ASCL2-XX1	476	328	217
XX1-AXIN2	552	331	419
MKI67-XX1	67	299	48
MCM3-XX1	188	3	26
UBE2C-XX1	10	204	21
XX1-LGR5	40	208	39
XX1-PTPRO	130	21	12
XX1-NKD1	763	801	539
XX1-HOXB8	740	178	411
XX1-HOXB9	436	464	287
XX1-PPA2	2399	2320	2659
XX1-RNF43	2127	1488	2140
XX1-XRCC6BP1	1475	1916	1732
XX1-XRCC6	2569	2278	2734
XX1-HOXB7	2533	2554	2708
XX1-HOXB13	2631	2463	1579
XX1-HOXA9	2006	1091	1823
XX1-HOXA11	1860	1984	2326
UNIDENTIFIED-UNIDENTIFIED COMBINATIONS			
XX1-XX15	35	107	245
XX1-XX110	112	763	101
XX1-XX182	2734	2582	2669
XX1-XX196	2689	2615	1964
XX1-XX2	86	190	231
XX1-XX20	105	386	15
XX1-XX205	2669	2499	2610
XX1-XX207	2671	2739	2733
XX1-XX33	194	194	360
XX1-XX35	430	600	654
XX1-XX34	1969	1397	2173
XX1-XX38	1968	1445	1509
XX1-XX49	21	340	303
XX1-XX47	115	814	119
XX1-XX44	1690	465	1070
XX1-XX45	1417	1830	2106

Table 3: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking using HSIC for different kernels. Total number of interactions per gene were 2743.

3.5.1. Unidentified-Identified combinations

- We first begin with the analysis of the unknown factor XX1 with some of the identified and confirmed factors that are implicated in the pathway either positively or negatively. As has been seen earlier many of the factors like RAD51AP1, RRM2, ASCL2, AXIN2, MKI67, LGR5 and NDK1 that are highly implicated in colorectal cancer case were found to be suppressed after the drug treatment. XX1 pairs with these factors and the pipeline assigns low rank to these combinations. One of the interpretations can be that XX1, like the above factors, is highly implicated in colorectal cancer case and its association with some of these factors might be possible in reality and entails verification of the same. For example, the minichromosome maintenance (MCM) proteins are essential replication factors and have been found to be overexpressed in colorectal cancer Ha et al. (2004). After the administration of the drug, MCM3 was found to be highly suppressed and the pipeline points to its low rank along with XX1. Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2C gene (UBE2C) Hao et al. (2012) is known to be overexpressed in colorectal cancer Takahashi et al. (2006) and its apparent downregulation after ETC-1922159 has been assigned a low rank with XX1. Genetic alterations in tyrosine phosphatases have been found in colorectal cancer and serve as tumor suppressors in colorectal cancer Laczmanska and Sasiadek (2011). PTPRO is one such family member and was found to be suppressed after drug treatment and assigned low ranks with XX1. There might be a possibility that mutations in PTPRO were present and there was overexpression of these mutated versions in the tumor cells before the drug administration. After the treatment, the in silico low ranks point to the observed suppressions in PTPRO. The HOX family, is known to play multiple roles in various tumor cases and varied affects have been found in colorectal tumor and normal cases Kanai et al. (2010). HOXB8 and HOXB9 are highly expressed in colorectal cancer cases and were found to be downregulated after the drug treatment. Along with XX1, they were assigned low ranks as desired.

The opposite interpretations are that there are very high ranks assigned to many of the factors that are known to play tumor suppressor roles like HOXB7, HOXB13, HOXA9, HOXA11 Kanai et al. (2010), PPA2 Cristóbal et al. (2014) and XRCC6BP1 and mutations in these could lead to enhancement in colorectal cancer. These were found to be down regulated after the drug treatment in cancer cases and were assigned high ranks along with the XX1. XX1 might be a tumor suppressor gene also that might be mutated in colorectal cancer case. But these high ranks provide an alternative insight to the functioning of XX1. Thus the interpretations are like two edges of one blade and biologists can use these rankings to see the multifaceted aspects of the hitherto unidentified XX1.

3.5.2. Unidentified-Unidentified combinations

- Now we analyse the unknown factor XX1 with some of the unknown/unexplored factors that are implicated in the pathway either positively or negatively. Observing table 3, the rankings of unidentified-unidentified factors after the ETC-1922159 were also generated.

In each of the series starting with XXM , where $M \in 1, 2, 3, 4$, two interactions are

shown with very low ranks assigned to them and two interactions are shown with very high ranks assigned to them. For example, XX1-XX20 and XX1-XX2 both show low priority ranks while XX1-XX205 and XX1-XX207 high ranks. The low priority ranks indicate that their down regulation was important after the ETC-1922159 treatment and these might have been highly expressed in colorectal cancer case before the treatment of the drug. The high priority ranks indicate that these might be tumor suppressor genes (might be mutated) in colorectal cancer and would be highly expressed after the administration of the drug, had the mutations not happened in them. Their down regulation and yet high rank points to their mutated versions in the cancerous cells, a possibility that needs to be verified. Similar interpretations can be made for the different ranked unidentified-unidentified combinations that the pipeline generated on the list of downregulated genes after the ETC-1922159 treatment.

4. Conclusion

4.1. Computational

A theoretically sound and a practical framework has been developed to prioritize higher order combinations of downregulated genes after the administration of ETC-1922159 PORCN-WNT inhibitor in CRC cells. The prioritization uses advanced density based sensitivity indices that exploit nonlinear relations in reproducing kernel hilbert spaces via kernel trick and support vector ranking method to rank and reveal various combinations of identified and unidentified factors that are affected after the drug treatment. This gives medical specialists/oncologists/biologists a way to navigate in a guided manner in a vast combinatorial forest thus cutting down cost in time/investment/energy as well as avoid cherry picking unknown biological hypotheses.

4.2. Biological

MYC upregulates PRC2 complex. PRC2 complex contains EZH2, which suppresses tumor suppressor genes via epigenetic modifications. MYC & HOXB8 are up regulated in CRC, but dual working mechanism of the same is not known. The pipeline showed ranking which correctly approximates and assigns low rank to this 3rd order combination of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2, thus pointing to down regulation by ETC-1922159. If the protein interaction and MYC-HOXB8 can be established and a study be done apropos EZH2, it will establish at in vitro/in vivo level, the in silico ranking also.

5. Availability and requirements

- Project name - Which gene combination to test in wet lab? R Code for Machine learning search engine using ETC-1922159 treated CRC static data
- Project home page - <https://zenodo.org/records/14636112>
- Operating system(s) - Platform independent

- Programming language - R statistical language R Development Core Team (2008)
- Other requirements - (1) SVM^{Rank} from https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html and (2) Sensitivity package in R from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>
- License - Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

6. Declarations

- Funding - No institute/university/NGO/company (private/public)/government organization was involved. The project was carried out on personal funds.
- Conflict of interest/Competing interests - There are no conflicts/competing interests to declare.
- Ethics approval and consent to participate - Not applicable.
- Consent for publication - Not applicable.
- Data availability - Data used in this research work has been released online publicly, in a publication in Madan et al. (2016). This data was made available in the form of supplementary table. Related to this data, on NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) Series GSE69687 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE69687>, click on **Download RNA-seq counts** button, it opens a page that contains **Human gene annotation table** (at the bottom of the page). The file **Human.GRCh38.p13.annot.tsv.gz** contains the range of genes with ENSEMBLGENEID all starting with ENSG. This ENSG identifier is used to index the recording of the regulated genes, in the data made available in the supplementary table in Madan et al. (2016). The data itself is available as supplementary material in the journal, however, the indexing of the genes used in the supplementary material is available on NCBI NIH database.
- Code availability - Code of the search engine used to generate the rankings has been made available on CERN based Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/records/14636112>.
- Author contribution - Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision -SS. Approval of manuscript - SS.
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